

Kinetics of Chlorination of Aniline and Substituted-anilines by *N,N*-Dichlorotoluene-*p*-sulphonamide in Buffered Water – Methanol Medium

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Kinetics of chlorination of aniline and substituted-anilines by *N,N*-dichlorotoluene-*p*-sulphonamide have been studied in acetate buffered 1 : 1 (v/v) water – methanol medium. The substituted-anilines studied were *p*-chloro, *p*-bromo, *p*-methyl, *p*-methoxy, *o*-chloro, *m*-chloro, *m*-nitro, 2,4-dichloro and *N*-methylanilines. The rates of chlorinations showed first order kinetics in [oxidant] and fractional order in [anilines]. The rates increased with increase in pH, showing inverse fractional order dependence in [H⁺]. Addition of the reduced product of the oxidant or the variation in ionic strength or dielectric constant of the reaction medium had little or negligible effects on the rates of reactions. Mechanisms consistent with the observed kinetics have been discussed and the related rate laws deduced. The coefficients of the rate-controlling steps have been calculated. The rate constants predicted from the rate laws as [anilines]¹ and [H⁺] vary are in reasonably good agreement with the experimental values.

AS a part of our mechanistic studies with *N,N*-dihalosulphonamides in partially aqueous media¹⁻³, we report herein the kinetics of chlorination of aniline and substituted-anilines by *N,N*-dichlorotoluene-*p*-sulphonamide in acetate buffered 1 : 1 (v/v) water – methanol medium.

Experimental

N,N-Dichlorotoluene-*p*-sulphonamide (dichloramine-T, DCT) was prepared by bubbling pure chlorine gas through the saturated aqueous solution of chloramine-T⁴. The fine white precipitate formed was filtered, dried on the filter paper by sucking dry air through it and then dried in a vacuum desiccator for 24 h. The purity of the oxidant was checked by iodometric estimation of the active chlorine present in it. Stock solution (~0.05 mol dm⁻³) of the compound in pure methanol was prepared, standardised and stored in dark coloured bottles.

Anilines studied were unsubstituted, *p*-chloro, *p*-bromo, *p*-methyl, *p*-methoxy, *o*-chloro, *m*-chloro, *m*-nitro, 2,4-dichloro and *N*-methylanilines. Accepted grades of anilines (Sisco) were used and redistilled or recrystallised before use. Stock solutions of the anilines (~0.10 mol dm⁻³) in pure methanol were prepared just before use. The ionic strength of the medium, was kept at 0.20 mol dm⁻³ with the concentrated aqueous solution of sodium perchlorate.

Kinetic measurement : The kinetic studies were made in 1 : 1 (v/v) acetate buffered water – methanol

media under pseudo-first order conditions with [anilines] >> [DCT] (5 – 20 fold excess). The reactions were initiated by the rapid addition of requisite amounts of DCT solution (0.0002 – 0.001 mol dm⁻³), pre-equilibrated at a desired temperature, to a solution containing known amounts of anilines (0.002 – 0.01 mol dm⁻³), acetate buffer, sodium perchlorate, methanol and water (to maintain 1 : 1 (v/v) water – methanol composition), pre-equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reactions were monitored for two half-lives by iodometric determination of unreacted oxidant in an aliquot of the reaction mixture at regular intervals of time. The pseudo-first order rate constants (*k*_{obs}) were computed by the graphical methods and the values were reproducible within ± 5% error.

Stoichiometry : The stoichiometry of DCT – anilines reactions were determined by equilibrating reaction mixtures containing slight excess of DCT over aniline concentrations in acetate buffered 1 : 1 (v/v) water – methanol medium. Estimation of unreacted oxidant in the reaction mixtures showed that two moles of anilines react with one mole of DCT. The observed stoichiometries may be represented by equation (1).

where, X = substituent. Under oxidant excess conditions varying stoichiometries were observed.

Product analysis : In all cases change of colour (violet) was observed on mixing the reactants. The

TABLE 1—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) FOR CHLORINATION OF ANILINE AND SUBSTITUTED-ANILINES BY *N,N*-DICHLOROTOLUENE-*p*-SULPHONAMIDE IN BUFFERED 1:1 (v/v) WATER-METHANOL MEDIUM AT 293 K ($I=0.20 \text{ mol dm}^{-2}$) AS $[DCT]_0$ AND $[ANILINES]$ ARE VARIED

$[DCT]_0$ $\times 10^4 \text{ mol dm}^{-2}$	$[Aniline]$ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-2}$	$k_{obs} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$									
		Ani	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -OH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	<i>m</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -Cl	2,4-diCl	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	N-Me
2.0	5.0	14.0	7.2	5.8	18.6	23.5	6.6	7.8	1.62	0.172	50.8
5.0	5.0	13.9	7.5	5.8	18.2	24.6	6.9	7.7	1.67	0.171	50.2
7.0	5.0	14.2	7.7	5.9	18.0	24.0	6.8	7.8	1.64	0.170	51.0
10.0	5.0	14.2	7.3	5.8	17.7	23.8	7.0	7.5	1.69	0.177	49.9
5.0	2.0	6.9	5.2	4.2	8.1	13.4	3.4	5.0	1.63	—	27.4
5.0	3.0	8.6	6.1	5.0	11.0	16.8	4.8	6.1	—	0.151	29.2
5.0	5.0	13.9	7.5	5.8	18.2	24.6	6.9	7.7	1.67	0.171	50.2
5.0	7.0	18.0	8.1	7.0	23.5	30.4	8.2	10.1	1.68	0.181	—
5.0	10.0	25.5	10.2	7.5	34.2	35.2	9.1	11.0	1.69	0.209	—

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING pH OF REACTION MEDIUM ON RATES OF CHLORINATIONS OF ANILINE AND SUBSTITUTED-ANILINES BY *N,N*-DICHLOROTOLUENE-*p*-SULPHONAMIDE IN 1:1 (v/v) WATER-METHANOL MEDIUM*

pH									$k_{obs} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$								
Ani	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	<i>m</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -Cl	2,4-diCl	N-Me	Ani	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	<i>m</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -Cl	2,4-diCl	N-Me
4.31	4.16	4.25	4.23	4.52	4.20	4.23	4.36	4.89	13.9	7.5	5.8	18.2	24.6	6.9	7.7	16.7	50.0
4.45	4.35	4.38	4.47	4.73	4.41	4.32	4.45	4.86	17.5	11.4	7.0	26.4	34.2	7.9	10.3	17.9	47.7
4.61	—	—	4.54	5.05	—	—	—	—	24.0	—	—	29.7	49.5	—	—	—	—
4.73	4.53	4.53	—	—	4.59	4.53	4.95	4.74	29.9	14.1	7.6	—	—	9.8	18.6	21.4	40.1
—	4.69	4.78	—	—	4.72	4.66	—	4.50	—	18.4	12.3	—	—	11.1	19.2	—	38.4

* $10^4 [DCT]_0 = 10^3 [Anilines]_0 = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-2}$, $I = 0.20 \text{ mol dm}^{-2}$, Temp = 293 K.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING IONIC STRENGTH AND DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF THE MEDIUM, AND ADDITION OF REACTION PRODUCT, TOLUENE-*p*-SULPHONAMIDE (TSA) ON RATES OF CHLORINATION OF ANILINES BY *N,N*-DICHLOROTOLUENE-*p*-SULPHONAMIDE*

I mol dm^{-2}	$k_{obs} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$			$[TSA]$ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-2}$	$k_{obs} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$			% Methanol % (v)	$k_{obs} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$					
	Ani	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br		Ani	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br		Ani	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	<i>m</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -Cl
0.1	13.1	7.3	5.4	0	13.9	7.5	5.8	40	24.2	12.7	—	31.2	10.4	14.6
0.2	13.9	7.5	5.8	1.0	13.2	7.1	6.1	45	17.4	9.9	7.7	22.0	8.8	11.0
0.3	13.4	7.8	5.7	3.0	13.4	7.1	5.8	50	13.9	7.5	5.8	18.2	6.9	7.7
0.5	13.4	—	—	5.0	13.4	7.1	5.7	60	9.0	4.1	3.5	10.3	3.9	5.0

* $10^4 [DCT]_0 = 10^3 [Anilines]_0 = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-2}$; Temp = 293 K.

colour showed absorption maxima at 530 nm and it may be due to the intermediate, *N*-chloroaniline. A tlc examination of the reaction products showed the presence of *o*-chloro and *p*-chloroanilines with the parent compound.

Toluene-*p*-sulphonamide (TSA), the reduced product of the oxidant was detected by paper chromatography.

Results and Discussion

Kinetics of chlorination of aniline and substituted-anilines by *N,N*-dichlorotoluene-*p*-sulphonamide have been studied in 1:1 (v/v) acetate buffered water-methanol media. The results are shown in Tables 1-5 and Figs. 1-4. At fixed pH and $[anilines]$ several fold excess over $[DCT]$, plots of $\log [DCT]$ vs time were linear upto two half-lives. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constants computed from the plots were unaffected

TABLE 4—KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR CHLORINATION OF ANILINE AND SUBSTITUTED-ANILINES BY *N,N*-DICHLOROTOLUENE-*p*-SULPHONAMIDE IN 1:1 (v/v) ACETATE BUFFERED WATER-METHANOL MEDIA

Anilines	Orders observed in		
	$[DCT]$	$[Sub]$	$[H^+]_{eff}$
Unsubst.	1	0.81	-0.81
<i>p</i> -Cl	1	0.42	-0.74
<i>p</i> -Br	1	0.35	-0.61
<i>p</i> -OH ₃	1	0.92	-0.67
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	1	0.70	-0.61
<i>m</i> -Cl	1	0.66	-0.49
<i>o</i> -Cl	1	0.53	-0.88
2,4-dichloro	1	0.10	-0.10
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	1	0.31	—
N-OH ₃	1	0.89	-0.49

*Computed from pH measurements.

by the changes in $[DCT]_0$ (Table 1), showing first order kinetics in $[DCT]$. At fixed $[DCT]_0$ and pH,

TABLE 5—COMPARISON OF CALCULATED AND OBSERVED THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR CHLORINATION OF ANILINE AND SUBSTITUTED-ANILINES BY *N,N*-DICHLOROTOLUENE-*p*-SULPHONAMIDE

Parameter	Aniline			<i>p</i> -Cl			<i>p</i> -Br			<i>p</i> -OH ₃			<i>m</i> -Cl		
	Set-I ^a	Set-II ^b	Set-III ^c	Set-I ^a	Set-II ^b	Set-III ^c	Set-I ^a	Set-II ^b	Set-III ^c	Set-I ^a	Set-II ^b	Set-III ^c	Set-I ^a	Set-II ^b	Set-III ^c
log <i>A</i>	8.13	12.1	11.3	4.86	8.6	8.5	7.9	8.6	6.6	5.2	4.2	6.2	9.4	9.8	10.0
<i>E</i> _a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	61.7	80.0	81.1	44.3	55.0	62.2	61.8	56.8	48.4	44.8	26.7	53.0	70.4	60.2	69.3
Δ <i>H</i> [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	59.0	61.2	54.8	41.8	52.4	64.4	62.7	56.0	46.2	42.3	22.7	44.3	68.0	54.2	112.2
Δ <i>S</i> [‡] (JK ⁻¹)	-98.2	-67.9	-115.2	-161.9	-89.3	-87.8	-87.5	-81.3	-150.7	-158.3	-178.6	-157.2	-73.1	-75.0	-62.8
Δ <i>G</i> [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	87.8	83.7	88.6	89.3	78.5	90.1	87.9	79.8	90.3	87.3	75.0	90.4	89.4	76.2	71.9

^aCalculated using the composite rate constants (*k*_{obs}). ^bCalculated using *k*_a values at different temperatures (Scheme 1 and eqn. 5). ^cCalculated using *k*_s values at different temperatures (Scheme 2 and eqn. 5).

 TABLE 6—COMPARISON OF CALCULATED AND EXPERIMENTAL RATE CONSTANTS FOR CHLORINATION OF ANILINE AND SUBSTITUTED-ANILINES BY *N,N*-DICHLOROTOLUENE-*p*-SULPHONAMIDE AS [ANILINE]₀ AND pH ARE VARIED

[Aniline] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	<i>k</i> _{obs} (× 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)						<i>k</i> _{cal} (× 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹) ^a					
	Ani	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -OH ₃	<i>m</i> -Cl	N-Me	Ani	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -OH ₃	<i>m</i> -Cl	N-Me
2.0	6.9	5.2	4.2	8.1	3.4	22.4	7.6	4.8	3.9	11.0	5.8	18.0
3.0	8.6	6.1	5.0	11.0	4.8	29.2	9.6	5.6	4.4	13.3	6.2	21.1
5.0	13.9	7.8	5.8	18.2	6.9	50.2	13.4	7.3	5.5	17.6	7.1	27.2
7.0	18.0	8.1	7.0	23.5	8.2	—	17.3	9.0	6.6	21.8	8.0	—
10.0	25.5	10.2	7.5	34.2	9.1	—	29.0	11.6	8.2	28.1	9.2	—
pH of the buffer soln. used to maintain pH ^b												
3.56	13.9	7.5	5.8	18.2	6.9	50.0	12.6	7.6	5.7	17.2	6.9	48.9
3.73	17.5	11.4	7.0	26.4	7.9	47.7	17.1	9.6	6.4	29.2	7.9	45.9
3.96	24.0	—	—	29.7	—	—	24.2	—	—	34.1	—	—
4.03	29.9	14.1	7.6	—	9.8	40.1	31.5	12.4	7.4	—	9.8	35.6
4.16	—	18.4	12.3	—	11.1	38.4	—	16.1	10.2	—	11.7	28.8

Calculated from the constants computed from the plots of ^a*k*_{obs} vs 1/[H⁺] ^b*k*_{obs} vs [S] (equation 5).

Fig. 1. Plots of (i) *k*_{obs} vs [Anilines] and (ii) 1/*k*_{obs} vs 1/[Anilines]; 10⁴ [DTC]₀ = 5.0 mol dm⁻³, *I* = 0.20 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 293 K, medium = acetate buffered 1 : 1 (v/v) water-methanol; (O) aniline, (V) *o*-Cl, (X) *m*-Cl, (●) *p*-Cl, (⊗) *p*-Br, (▼) *p*-OH₃, and (□) *p*-OCH₃.

Fig. 2. Plots of (i) *k*_{obs} vs 1/[H⁺] and (ii) 1/*k*_{obs} vs [H⁺]; 10⁴ [DTC]₀ = 10³ [Anilines]₀ = 5.0 mol dm⁻³, *I* = 0.20 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 293 K, medium = acetate buffered 1 : 1 (v/v) water-methanol; (O) aniline, (V) *o*-Cl, (X) *m*-Cl, (●) *p*-Cl, (⊗) *p*-Br, (□) *p*-OCH₃, and (■) N-Me.

Fig. 3. Plots of (a) $\log k_{obs}$ vs σ and (b) ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger , $10^4[DCT]_0 = 10^3[Anilines]_0 = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.20 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 293 K, medium = acetate buffered 1 : 1 (v/v) water - methanol: (O) aniline, (V) *o*-Cl, (x) *m*-Cl, (●) *p*-Cl, (⊗) *p*-Br, (▼) *p*-CH₃, (□) *p*-OCH₃ and (■) *m*-NO₂.

Fig. 4. Plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs % methanol; $10^4[DCT]_0 = 10^3[Anilines]_0 = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.20 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 293 K: (O) aniline, (V) *o*-Cl, (●) *p*-Cl, (⊗) *p*-Br and (▼) *p*-CH₃.

the rates increased with increase in [anilines] (Table 1) and the plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [anilines]$

were linear with fractional slopes, indicating fractional order dependence (Table 4). The plots of k_{obs} vs [aniline] were generally linear with finite intercepts on the ordinates (Fig 1), probably signalling the two-pathway mechanism for the chlorination of anilines. The rates increased with increase in pH with inverse fractional order dependences in $[H^+]$ (Tables 2 and 4). The plots of k_{obs} vs $1/[H^+]$ or pH were also linear in most cases, with finite intercepts (Fig. 2).

Addition of the reaction product or the variation in ionic strength of the reaction medium had negligible effects on the rates of chlorinations (Table 3). But the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium by increasing methanol composition decreased the rate. The plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs % CH₃OH or $1/D$ were linear with negative slopes.

The rates were measured at different temperatures and the activation parameters have been computed from the Arrhenius plots.

Mechanisms of oxidations: The following equilibria are likely to exist²⁻⁸ in partially aqueous solutions of *N,N*-dichlorotoluene-*p*-sulphonamide,

Hence, the kinetics of first order in [DCT], fractional order in [substrate] and inverse fractional order in $[H^+]$ observed with most anilines may be explained by two-pathway mechanism, one through the direct interaction of $ArSO_2NCl_2$ with the substrate and the other through the formation of HOCl.

where S is substrate (anilines).

The related combined rate law is

$$-\frac{d[DCT]}{dt} = K_1 k_2 \frac{[DCT][SH^+]}{[H^+]} + k_3 [DCT] \quad (4)$$

or

$$-\frac{d[DCT]}{[DCT]dt} = K_1 k_2 \frac{[SH^+]}{[H^+]} + k_3$$

or

$$k_{obs} = K_1 k_2 \frac{[SH^+]}{[H^+]} + k_3 = k_2^- [S] + k_3 \quad (5)$$

The plots of k_{obs} vs $[S]$ and k_{obs} vs $1/[H^+]$ were linear with finite intercepts on the ordinates (Figs. 1 and 2) in accordance with rate law (5). Two sets of constants $K_1 k_2$ and k_3 were calculated from the

slopes and intercepts of the above plots, one set from the plots of k_{obs} vs $[S]$ and the other from the plots of k_{obs} vs $1/[H^+]$. These constants were used to predict the rate constants as $[S]$ or $[H^+]$ varied. The predicted values compared with the experimental rate constants are shown in Table 6. Reasonably good agreement between the two sets of values supports the two-pathway mechanism.

o-Chloro and *p*-methoxyanilines were exceptions to the two-pathway mechanism. The plots of k_{obs} vs $[S]$ attained the limiting values in these cases, while the double reciprocal plots were linear (Fig. 1). Thus the results observed may be explained by Michaelis-Menten type mechanism (Scheme 3); modified Scheme 1 as the reverse reactions may be appreciable in these cases.

The related rate law is

$$-\frac{d[\text{DCT}]}{dt} = \frac{K_2 k_4 [\text{DCT}][\text{S}]}{1 + K_2[\text{S}]} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_4 [\text{DCT}][\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_1 K_2 [\text{SH}^+]} \quad (6)$$

or

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K_2 k_4 [\text{S}]}{1 + K_2[\text{S}]} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_4 [\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_1 K_2 [\text{SH}^+]} \quad (7)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{1}{K_2 k_4 [\text{S}]} + \frac{1}{k_4} = \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_1 K_2 k_4 [\text{SH}^+]} + \frac{1}{k_4} \quad (8)$$

The plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[S]$ and $1/k_{obs}$ vs $[H^+]$ were linear (Figs. 1 and 2) in conformity with rate law (8).

The detailed mechanism of chlorination is shown in Scheme 4.

Scheme 4

The formation of characteristic colour observed prior to the formation of products shows the formation of the *N*-chloro intermediate, which has

an absorption maximum at 530 nm. The intensity of the colour increases, reaches a maximum intensity and then decreases. The formation of the *N*-chloro intermediate is also supported by the observation that there is negligible reaction between *N,N*-dichlorotoluene-*p*-sulphonamide and acetanilide (containing an electron-withdrawing *N*-acetyl group) under identical reaction conditions. Further, the introduction of the nitro group to the benzene ring decreased the rate by about 100 times. Formation of *N*-chloro intermediates in the chlorination of anilines has also been noticed in a number of cases^{9,10}.

The rates of chlorinations of *o*-chloro and *p*-chloroanilines were about one-half of the value for aniline (Table 1), while the rate of 2,4-dichloroaniline is about one-tenth of the value for the parent compound. Replacement of one of the hydrogen atoms of NH_2 group by methyl group almost tripled the rate of chlorination. Electron-releasing substituents such as methyl group generally increased the rate, while electron-withdrawing substituents decreased the rate (Table 1).

A free radical mechanistic component of some significance is also probable. Relatively large negative entropy of activation and high positive free energy of activation may suggest the role of bond-breaking in attaining the activated state. Plot of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger was also linear with an isokinetic temperature of 306 K which is closer to the temperature range employed in the present investigations (283–298 K). Applicability of Hammett equation¹¹ has also been tested. Equation (9) is found to be valid with the anilines for which σ values were available¹² (Fig. 4).

$$\log k_{obs} = -2.9 - \sigma \quad (9)$$

The observed decrease of rate with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium (Table 3) is in conformity with Amis-Jaffe equation (10)^{12,13} for dipolar molecule-dipolar molecule interactions,

$$\log k_D = \log k_\infty - \frac{2\mu_1\mu_2}{2.303 k_B T r^3 D} \quad (10)$$

where, k_D and k_∞ are the rate constants in media of dielectric constants D and ∞ , respectively, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, μ_1 and μ_2 are permanent moments on the dipoles, r is the distance of approach for the dipoles and T the absolute temperature.

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